

Role of ELISA in Screening of Blood Donors for Viral Hepatitis B & C in A Tertiary Care Hospital in Jamshedpur

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Abstract:

Background: Hepatitis B and C are significant global health concerns due to their potential to cause chronic liver diseases, including cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma. Blood transfusion remains a key transmission route, especially in regions with less stringent screening protocols. The Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) is widely used for detecting Hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) and anti-HCV antibodies, helping to mitigate the risk of transfusion-transmitted infections (TTIs).

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the role of ELISA in screening blood donors for Hepatitis B and C at a tertiary care hospital in Jamshedpur, India, and to assess the predominance of these infections among the donor population.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted over six months, involving 300 voluntary blood donors at a tertiary care hospital. Blood samples were collected and tested using ELISA for HBsAg and anti-HCV antibodies. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, with Chi-square tests employed to assess associations between demographic variables and ELISA results.

Results: The study found that 5% of donors tested positive for HBsAg, while 3.33% tested positive for anti-HCV antibodies. No significant associations were observed between demographic factors (such as age, gender, and occupation) and the likelihood of testing positive for either infection.

Conclusion: The ELISA method proved effective in identifying Hepatitis B and C infections among blood donors. The study highlights the importance of routine and universal screening in blood donation practices to ensure the safety of blood transfusions.

Recommendations: There is a need for continuous and stringent screening protocols using ELISA in all blood donation centers. Further studies are recommended to monitor the predominance of Hepatitis B and C in different regions and populations to improve public health strategies and reduce the burden of these infections.

Keywords: Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C, ELISA, Blood Donors, Transfusion-Transmitted Infections.

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Introduction

Hepatitis B and C are among the most common viral infections in the world, and they pose significant public health risks because they can cause chronic liver illnesses such as cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma. According to the WHO, an estimated 296 million people were living with chronic (HBV) infection in 2019, with around 58 million affected by chronic (HCV) infection [1]. These infections are primarily spread by contact with infected blood and bodily fluids; hence blood transfusions are an essential area for screening to reduce transmission.

Low- and middle-income countries continue to face a high risk of (TTIs) due to lax guidelines and screening processes. The ELISA has substantially

improved the detection of HBsAg and anti-HCV antibodies, making it a reliable and sensitive method for screening blood donors [2]. The ability of ELISA to produce consistent results in a range of situations makes it an invaluable tool in the global effort to prevent hepatitis virus transmission via blood transfusions.

India, where this study was conducted, continues to have a significant burden of Hepatitis B and C infections. According to research conducted in various areas of India, the predominance of HBsAg among blood donors ranges from 2% to 8%, while the predominance of anti-HCV antibodies ranges from 0.5% to 3.5% [3, 4]. These findings highlight the significance of comprehensive screening

measures in blood donation practices to reduce the incidence of TTIs and protect public health. This study aims to evaluate the role of ELISA in screening blood donors for Hepatitis B and C at a tertiary care hospital in Jamshedpur, India, and to assess the predominance of these infections among the donor population.

Methodology

Study Design: This is a cross-sectional study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at a tertiary care hospital in Jamshedpur, a key medical facility serving the region's population. The study was conducted over a period of six months.

Participants: A total of 300 voluntary blood donors were included in the study. Donors were selected randomly from those who visited the blood donation center during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

- Voluntary blood donors aged between 18 and 60 years.
- Donors who provided informed consent for participating in the study.
- Donors with no history of viral hepatitis or chronic liver disease.

Exclusion Criteria

- Donors with a history of recent illness, surgery, or chronic conditions such as HIV, diabetes, or hypertension.
- Donors who did not provide informed consent.
- Donors who had previously tested positive for Hepatitis B or C.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, donors were selected randomly, and the inclusion criteria were strictly adhered to. Additionally, laboratory technicians and data analysts were blinded to the donors' personal information to reduce observer bias.

Data Collection: Data were gathered using a standardised data collecting form. The form contained demographic information, medical history, and ELISA screening results for (HBsAg) and anti-HCV antibodies.

Procedure: Blood samples were collected from each donor under sterile conditions. The samples were then subjected to ELISA testing to detect the existence of anti-HCV antibodies and HBsAg. The ELISA kits used were approved and validated for clinical use. All tests were conducted following the manufacturer's guidelines and standard laboratory protocols.

Statistical Analysis: The data were analysed with SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarise donor demographics as well as the predominance of Hepatitis B and C. The Chi-square test was used to determine the statistical significance of relationships between demographic characteristics and viral markers. A p-value of <0.05 was considered significant.

Results

The donors were screened for (HBsAg) and Hepatitis C (anti-HCV antibodies) using the (ELISA).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Blood Donors

Characteristic	Number of Donors (n = 300)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	210	70%
Female	90	30%
Age Group		
18-30 years	120	40%
31-40 years	90	30%
41-50 years	60	20%
51-60 years	30	10%
Occupation		
Office Workers	100	33.3%
Manual Laborers	120	40%
Students	50	16.7%
Others	30	10%

The results of the ELISA tests for HBsAg and anti-HCV antibodies are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Results of ELISA Screening for Hepatitis B and C

Test	Positive (n)	Negative (n)	Percentage Positive (%)
HBsAg	15	285	5%
Anti-HCV	10	290	3.33%

Out of 300 donors, 15 (5%) tested positive for (HBsAg), and 10 (3.33%) tested positive for (anti-HCV).

The association between demographic variables (age, gender, and occupation) and ELISA test results was analyzed using the Chi-square test. The results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Association between Demographic Variables and ELISA Results

Variable	HBsAg Positive (n = 15)	HBsAg Negative (n = 285)	p-value	Anti-HCV Positive (n = 10)	Anti-HCV Negative (n = 290)	p-value
Gender						
Male	10	200	0.24	8	202	0.31
Female	5	85		2	88	
Age Group						
18-30 years	3	117	0.45	2	118	0.52
31-40 years	5	85		4	86	
41-50 years	4	56		3	57	
51-60 years	3	27		1	29	
Occupation						
Office Workers	4	96	0.76	3	97	0.62
Manual Laborers	7	113		5	115	
Students	2	48		1	49	
Others	2	28		1	29	

No statistically significant association was found between the demographic variables (gender, age group, occupation) and the positivity for HBsAg or anti-HCV ($p > 0.05$ for all comparisons).

Statistical Analysis Summary

- The predominance of Hepatitis B among the blood donors was 5%, while the predominance of Hepatitis C was 3.33%.
- The analysis did not reveal any significant association between demographic characteristics (gender, age, and occupation) and the likelihood of testing positive for either Hepatitis B or C.
- The overall seropositivity for Hepatitis B and C combined was 8.33%.

Discussion

Out of 300 blood donors, 5% tested positive for (HBsAg), and 3.33% tested positive for Hepatitis C virus antibodies (anti-HCV). These findings indicate a non-negligible predominance of these viral infections among the donor population, underscoring the importance of routine screening in preventing the transmission of these blood-borne pathogens.

The demographic research found that 70% of the donors were male, with the bulk falling between the ages of 18 and 30. Despite these demographic distributions, no significant association was found between gender, age, or occupation and the likelihood of testing positive for either Hepatitis B or C. This suggests that the risk of infection is relatively uniform across different demographic groups within this donor population, reinforcing the need for universal screening regardless of demographic factors.

In summary, the ELISA method proved to be a reliable tool for detecting Hepatitis B and C among blood donors. The overall seropositivity rate of 8.33% highlights the critical role of thorough screening processes in blood donation programs to ensure the safety of transfusion practices. Given the lack of significant demographic predictors, the study supports the implementation of universal screening protocols to mitigate the risk of viral transmission through blood products.

Adeleke et al. (2021) investigated the sensitivity and specificity of fast diagnostic tests (RDTs) and ELISA for detecting (HBsAg) in blood donors. The study discovered that the ELISA approach detected a considerably greater frequency of HBV infection (14.6%) than the RDTs (5.7%). RDTs had a comparatively low sensitivity of 31.4% but a high specificity of 98.7%, indicating that ELISA is more trustworthy for screening in high-risk populations [5].

Similarly, Bajpai et al. (2021) compared the performance of two RDTs and the Chemiluminescence Immunoassay (CLIA) to ELISA for screening blood donors. They discovered that both RDTs and CLIA had poorer sensitivity than ELISA, resulting in considerable false positives and negatives. The study indicated that, while CLIA may be appropriate for emergency screenings, ELISA is still more accurate for regular blood donor screening [6].

Ibrahim et al. (2019) investigated the validity of RDTs versus ELISA in public hospitals in Kaduna, Nigeria. The study found that RDTs have limited sensitivity for identifying HBsAg and Hepatitis C virus (HCV) antibodies (40% and 50%, respectively). The findings emphasised the importance of ELISA, as recommended by the

WHO, in minimising the risk of hepatitis transmission through blood transfusions [7].

Dhiman et al. (2019) found that utilising ELISA in combination with a detailed family history analysis improved the detection of consecutive reactive findings (TTIs). This method aids in the identification of probable false positives and guarantees that donors who have had intimate contact with infected patients are correctly recognised [8].

Conclusion

The ELISA method proved effective in identifying Hepatitis B and C among the blood donors. The study focused on the importance of routine screening to prevent the transmission of these viruses through blood transfusion. The lack of a significant association between demographic factors and seropositivity suggests that all demographic groups should be screened equally, reinforcing the need for universal screening protocols in blood donation settings.

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